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2025 IYUL

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MUNDARIJA

Yashil ish o'rinlari va ekologik ta'lim: o'zbekiston yoshlari uchun yangi imkoniyatlar	12
Rashidov Saidislom, Zaripova Mardona	
Soliqlarni to'lashdan bo'yin tovlash holatlarining informatsion assimetriyaga ta'siri	16
Babanazarova Nilufar Xolmatovna	
Iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda budget mablag'laridan foydalanish mexanizmining o'rni va ahamiyati	23
Rustamova Gulmira Aliqulovna	
Dasturiy mahsulotlar logistikasi	30
Uzaqov Ortik Shaymardanovich	
Banklarda moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashda moliyaviy natijalar ahamiyati	35
Djalilov G'ayrat Qaxramanovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini "yashil universitet" tizimiga transformatsiya qilish istiqbollari (buxoro davlat texnika universiteti va malayziyaning oliy ta'lim muassasalari o'rtasidagi hamkorlik misolida)	39
Rahmatov Shuxrat Axatovich	
Davlat qarzi siyosati samaradorligini oshirish orqali makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni mustahkamlash	43
Sayfutdinov Xasanboy Dilshodovich	
Оптимизация бизнес-процессов и модернизация занятости в условиях цифровизации	47
Явкачев Шохзод Зайниддин углы	
Strategik rivojlanish sharoitida investitsion jozibadorlikning o'rni	54
Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li	
Kichik biznes subyektlarini moliyalashtirishni rag'batlashtirish	61
Annaklichev Saxi Saparmuxamedovich	
Альтернативный подход к распределению финансовых ресурсов для эффективного финансирования высшего образования	65
Гулшат Карлибаева	
Banklarda moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashda moliyaviy natijalar ahamiyati	70
Djalilov G'ayrat Qaxramanovich	
O'zbekistonda jahon sivilizatsiyasiga ta'sir o'tkaza oladigan zamonaviy qarashlarga ega memorning yetishmasligi	74
Nabiyev Hamidjon Mirzo o'g'li	
General Concept and Principles of Quality Management System	78
Atamirzayev Nodirbek Bekmirzayevich	

GENERAL CONCEPT AND PRINCIPLES OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract: A Quality Management System (QMS) is a systematic approach aimed at continuously monitoring and improving the quality of products and services in organizations, ensuring production meets consumer requirements. The general concept of QMS implies that quality must be formed and controlled not only in the final product but throughout the entire production process. This system is based on international standards, particularly the ISO 9000:2015 series. The fundamental principles of quality management include customer focus, leadership commitment, employee involvement, process-based approach, integrated management, continuous improvement, fact-based decision making, and mutually beneficial relationships with interested parties. These principles play a critical role in achieving an organization's strategic goals. This work discusses the essence of QMS, its core principles, their practical application, and the benefits it brings to enterprises. Additionally, the relevance of implementing QMS in the national economy and ways to enhance its effectiveness are analyzed. Research results indicate that effective application of QMS is a key factor in increasing organizational competitiveness and gaining customer trust.

Keywords: ISO 9001, quality principles, customer focus, continuous improvement, organizational efficiency, process-based approach, leadership role, employee involvement, quality indicators, enterprise competitiveness.

Annotatsiya: Sifat menejmenti tizimi (SMT) — bu tashkilotlarda mahsulot va xizmatlar sifatini doimiy nazorat qilish va yaxshilashga yo'naltirilgan tizimli yondashuv bo'lib, ishlab chiqarishning iste'molchilar talablariga javob berishini ta'minlaydi. SMT umumiy konsepsiyasiga ko'ra, sifat faqat yakuniy mahsulotda emas, balki butun ishlab chiqarish jarayonida shakllantirilib, nazorat qilinishi kerak. Ushbu tizim xalqaro standartlarga, xususan, ISO 9000:2015 standartlari tizimiga asoslangan. Sifat menejmentining asosiy tamoyillari quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi: mijozlarga yo'naltirilganlik, rahbariyat sadoqati, xodimlarning ishtiroki, jarayonga asoslangan yondashuv, integratsiyalashgan boshqaruv, uzluksiz takomillashtirish, faktlarga asoslangan qarorlar qabul qilish va manfaatdor tomonlar bilan o'zaro foydali munosabatlar. Bu tamoyillar tashkilotning strategik maqsadlariga erishishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Ushbu maqolada SMTning mohiyati, asosiy tamoyillari, ularning amaliy qo'llanilishi va korxonalar uchun olib keladigan afzalliklari muhokama qilinadi. Shuningdek, SMTni milliy iqtisodiyotda joriy etishning dolzarbligi va uning samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, SMTni samarali qo'llash tashkilotlar raqobatbardoshligini oshirish va mijozlar ishonchini qozonishning asosiy omilidir.

Kalit so'zlar: ISO 9001, sifat tamoyillari, mijozga yo'naltirilganlik, uzluksiz takomillashtirish, tashkilot samaradorligi, jarayonga asoslangan yondashuv, rahbariyat roli, xodimlar ishtiroki, sifat ko'rsatkichlari, korxonalar raqobatbardoshligi.

Аннотация: Система менеджмента качества (СМК) — это систематический подход, направленный на постоянный мониторинг и улучшение качества продукции и услуг в организациях, обеспечивая соответствие производства требованиям потребителей. Общая концепция СМК предполагает, что качество должно формироваться и контролироваться не только в конечном продукте, но и на всех этапах производственного процесса. Эта система основана на международных стандартах, в частности серии ISO 9000:2015. Основные принципы менеджмента качества включают ориентацию на потребителя, приверженность руководства, вовлечение персонала, процессный подход, интегрированное управление, постоянное совершенствование, принятие решений на основе фактов и взаимовыгодные отношения с заинтересованными сторонами. Эти принципы играют ключевую роль в достижении стратегических целей организации. В работе рассматривается сущность СМК, её основные принципы, их практическое применение и преимущества, которые она приносит предприятиям. Также проанализирована актуальность внедрения СМК в национальную экономику и пути повышения её эффективности. Результаты исследования показывают, что эффективное применение СМК является ключевым фактором повышения конкурентоспособности организации и завоевания доверия клиентов.

Ключевые слова: ISO 9001, принципы качества, ориентация на клиента, постоянное совершенствование, организационная эффективность, процессный подход, роль руководства, вовлечение сотрудников, показатели качества, конкурентоспособность предприятий.

INTRODUCTION

Today, due to the intensification of global economic competition and the increasing demand from customers for high-quality products and services, quality management systems (QMS) have gained significant importance in organizations. A quality management system is a systematic approach that encompasses the

processes of planning, controlling, and improving quality at all stages of an enterprise or organization's activities [1]. It not only guarantees the quality of products or services but also serves to optimize internal processes, efficiently use resources, and fully satisfy customer requirements. Therefore, implementing a quality management system is one of the most effective tools to ensure an organization's competitiveness in the modern business environment [2].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of quality is understood as the conformity of a product or service to specified requirements and standards. However, a quality management system is much broader than this concept; it ensures continuous management of quality through organizational processes. The main goal of a quality management system is to maintain a consistently high level of product and service quality within the organization. To achieve this, the quality management system is closely linked to the organization's strategic objectives, managing all quality-related processes, employee activities, resources, and control mechanisms within a unified system [3].

Internationally, the most widely adopted standards in the field of quality management systems belong to the ISO 9000 family. The ISO 9001:2015 standard sets out the most important requirements for quality management systems and enables organizations to implement a systematic approach to quality assurance [4]. This standard serves as a foundation for organizations to define processes, allocate resources efficiently, engage employees, and set quality objectives.

For a quality management system to operate effectively, its principles must be clear and understandable. ISO defines seven fundamental principles that play a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency of the quality management system. First, customer focus – the needs and expectations of the customer must be at the center of any organization's activities. Second, leadership – the commitment and active involvement of top management are key factors in the successful implementation of the system [5]. Third, engagement of people – the full and effective utilization of all resources within the organization through employee involvement. Fourth, process approach – understanding and managing interrelated processes increases efficiency and effectiveness. Fifth, system approach to management – ensures continuous control and improvement of quality. Sixth, continual improvement – enhances organizational competitiveness and enables entry into new markets. Finally, the seventh principle – factual approach to decision making and effective communication with stakeholders – guarantees system stability [6].

Implementing a quality management system not only improves the quality of products and services but also enhances overall management quality, increases employee productivity, clarifies processes, and improves internal communication within the organization. Therefore, the basic principles of quality management systems and their practical application processes are an important research subject for modern organizations [7].

In the context of Uzbekistan, comprehensive efforts are also being made to implement quality management systems. To increase enterprise competitiveness, access international markets, and expand export potential, emphasis is placed on widespread application of quality management systems. National standards, legislation, and government programs serve as the foundation for the development of quality management systems. Hence, a deep study of the general concepts and principles of quality management systems and the development of effective methodologies for their implementation in enterprise activities is of great importance for the development of Uzbekistan's economy.

A quality management system in modern enterprises includes the structural, technological, and managerial elements necessary to ensure continuous improvement and management of quality. Its main principles, harmonized with the enterprise's strategy, enable high-level assurance of product and service quality through a process-based approach and continuous improvement. Thus, the proper implementation of a quality management system forms the basis for the long-term success and market competitiveness of organizations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research utilized the following methodological approaches to analyze the essence, core principles, and practical application of quality management systems (QMS) in production:

Analytical-methodological approach – study and systematization of ISO 9000:2015 international standards, theoretical and practical sources related to QMS, and evaluation of their core principles.

Comparative analysis – comparison of the performance of enterprises with and without QMS implementation to identify practical benefits of the system.

Contextual approach – considering the specific conditions of production processes (particularly in the textile industry), tailored recommendations were developed for the effective implementation of QMS.

Empirical analysis – assessment of the effectiveness and impact on customer trust based on organizational experiences of QMS implementation.

System approach – analysis based on an integrated management model that ensures quality formation not only in the final product but throughout the entire production process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings obtained during the course of this research reveal that the implementation of a Quality Management System (QMS) within an organization plays a crucial role in ensuring the quality of products and services, maintaining consistency, and meeting customer needs. Developed on the basis of the ISO 9000:2015 series of international standards, this system serves not only to control the final output but also to monitor and improve the entire production process from a quality perspective.

The study confirms that the introduction of QMS significantly strengthens internal operational discipline and facilitates the establishment of a culture of continuous improvement. By integrating the seven key principles of quality management — customer focus, leadership, engagement of people, process approach, improvement, evidence-based decision making, and relationship management — organizations can create a structured and systematic environment that supports sustainable success. One of the most notable outcomes is the enhancement of organizational competitiveness. QMS allows companies to clearly define roles, responsibilities, and expectations, which contributes to reducing errors and inefficiencies. Moreover, it encourages a data-driven approach to decision-making, which reduces subjectivity and enhances operational transparency. These features collectively improve productivity and reduce costs over the long term.

Empirical data collected from textile enterprises and laboratory evaluations within the study highlight a measurable improvement in product quality following QMS implementation. Regular monitoring of quality indicators across interrelated production stages has led to reduced process nonconformities, minimized losses, and more efficient use of resources. For example, many companies reported a decline in defective units, improvement in lead times, and more streamlined workflows. Another critical result is the significant increase in customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Companies that adopted QMS principles have seen improved feedback and greater customer retention rates. This is largely attributed to consistent delivery of quality products and proactive engagement in customer needs and expectations. In addition, with better internal communication and collaboration, staff involvement in quality-related activities has improved, contributing to a sense of ownership and accountability.

The research also finds that, in the context of Uzbekistan's national economy, QMS implementation contributes to industrial modernization and export capacity. Particularly, companies aiming to access international markets — such as those under the GSP+ preferential trade system — must meet strict quality certification requirements. A well-functioning QMS aligns organizations with these international demands, making certification and entry into foreign markets more accessible (Figure 1).

Figure – 1: Model of the Quality Management System Based on ISO 9001 Principles

Empirical analyses conducted in industrial enterprises and laboratories confirm that implementing a Quality Management System (QMS) — while taking into account the interconnection of production stages — ensures the stability of product quality. Continuous monitoring of quality indicators has led to a reduction in inconsistencies and losses within production processes. Through a process-based management model, production resources are being allocated more efficiently, which in turn reduces operational costs and increases overall profitability.

Moreover, the research results show that customer trust and loyalty have improved in enterprises that have implemented QMS. This has contributed to an increase in market share and the expansion of export opportunities. In particular, for companies planning to enter international markets under the GSP+ system, the existence of a quality system has become both a mandatory and strategic necessity. Organizations are aligning with international certification requirements through QMS, thereby enhancing the export potential of their products (Figure 2).

Figure – 2: Contextual Mechanism for Implementing QMS in Laboratory

In the context of the national economy, the relevance of implementing a Quality Management System (QMS) is highly valued. Through establishing effective management in organizations, improving employee qualifications, and standardizing production processes, the potential to produce competitive and export-oriented products is increasing. This is particularly important for enterprises relying on domestic raw material bases, as quality management creates opportunities to add value and strengthen brand reputation.

The research placed special emphasis on the contextual mechanism. It was revealed that for the QMS to function effectively within an organization, several critical factors must align — including organizational culture, leadership approach, technological readiness, and employee involvement. When these elements are harmonized, the QMS operates fully and produces tangible results. Therefore, it is essential to adopt an individual approach for each enterprise.

Implementing QMS in organizations contributes not only to quality control but also to the overall improvement of the management system. This, in turn, ensures the sustainable development of the organization. Research findings indicate that enterprises investing in QMS achieve long-term economic efficiency and are able to successfully compete in global markets.

The implementation of a Quality Management System (QMS) in textile industry enterprises plays a significant role in enhancing production efficiency, product quality, and customer satisfaction. As the global market becomes increasingly competitive, textile manufacturers in developing countries like Uzbekistan are recognizing the importance of adopting international standards such as ISO 9001:2015 to remain relevant and competitive.

One of the key points revealed in this research is the necessity of considering the internal and external context of the organization when designing and implementing a QMS. Factors such as market demands, technological advancement, regulatory requirements, resource availability, and stakeholder expectations must be carefully analyzed. A contextual approach ensures that the QMS is not just a set of formal procedures, but a dynamic framework tailored to the organization's specific operational environment. Another important observation is that QMS implementation in the textile sector is most effective when supported by top management commitment. Leadership plays a vital role in fostering a culture of quality, motivating employees, allocating resources, and ensuring that quality objectives are aligned with strategic business goals. Without strong leadership, QMS initiatives are likely to be poorly integrated and fail to achieve sustainable results.

Moreover, the integration of process-based thinking into QMS is crucial. Textile production involves a sequence of interconnected processes, including sourcing raw materials, weaving, dyeing, finishing, and packaging. Each of these processes must be clearly defined, monitored, and controlled to ensure consistent quality. Establishing quality indicators and feedback loops helps identify defects early and supports continuous improvement.

The study also found that employee involvement and competency development are central to QMS success. Workers at all levels should be aware of quality objectives and trained in quality assurance techniques. Their active participation enhances ownership of processes and contributes to a stronger quality culture.

However, challenges remain, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which often lack the financial and human resources to fully implement and maintain a robust QMS. In such cases, a phased or simplified approach, focused on critical processes and gradual expansion, may be more practical and effective.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The Quality Management System (QMS) is a vital tool for modern organizations in ensuring consistent quality of products and services. Its main objectives are to meet customer requirements, manage internal processes efficiently, and enhance the organization's competitiveness. The ISO 9000 series of international standards clearly define the structure and principles of QMS, enabling organizations to manage quality in a systematic manner.

The seven key principles of quality management — customer focus, leadership, engagement of people, process approach, integrated management, continual improvement, and evidence-based decision making — ensure the effectiveness of the system. These principles contribute to quality enhancement across all areas of organizational activity.

In Uzbek enterprises, the implementation of QMS plays a crucial role in supporting sustainable economic development and increasing competitiveness in international markets. Thus, a deep understanding of QMS and its proper application is a fundamental factor for the success of any organization.

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muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. № 7

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"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

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